

Iron(II) Complexation with 4-Amino-5-Nitroso-2,6-Pyrimidinediol

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FASCINATED by the analytical potentialities of pyridinols¹, it was thought worthwhile to investigate the similar aspects of biologically important pyrimidines. The presence of two electronegative annular nitrogen atoms separated by one carbon atom and suitable substituents in other positions make them attractive analytically. In the course of study, it is found that the compound 4-amino-5-nitroso-2,6-pyrimidinediol abbreviated as ANP_mD (I) reacts selectively with Fe(II), Co(II) and Ru(III).

In the present communication, the results of its complexation with Fe(II) and subsequent detection and determination (spectrophotometric and chelometric) of the metal, are reported.

Experimental

Standard solutions of the reagent and iron(II) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of ANP_mD (K & K Laboratories, Inc., U.S.A.) and Mohr's salt in double distilled water. Hydroxylamine hydrochloride was added to iron(II) solution to prevent its oxidation. The pH of the solutions were adjusted using acetate buffers and checked with a Metrohm pH meter, type E-350. Absorbance measurements were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer.

Results and Observations

When few drops of aqueous ANP_mD solution (light red in colour) were added to iron(II) solution, blue colouration resulted. The characteristics of the blue complex were studied spectrophotometrically. It exhibited λ_{max} at 610 nm (ϵ 15,000) and its absorbance remained maximum and constant in between pH 5.5 and 7.0. Nearly 90 times of the molar excess of the reagent was needed for full colour development. The complex contained iron and ANP_mD in 1:2 molar ratio and it obeyed Beer's law up to 3.4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of iron concentration. Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction was calculated to be 0.0037 $\mu\text{g Fe/cm}^2$ for 0.001 absorbance. As the absorption by the reagent at λ_{max} of the complex (610 nm) was not negligible, reagent blanks were used in all the studies.

Detection of iron(II): Place a drop of the test solution on a spot plate or filter paper (Whatman No. 1), add a drop each of 1% hydroxylamine hydrochloride (to reduce any Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺), sodium acetate (10%) and ANP_mD solution (0.01 M). A blue colour develops instantaneously if iron(II) is present.

Limits of identification: 0.04 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on spot plate; 0.11 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on filter paper.

Limits of dilution: 1:1,320,000 on spot plate; 1:450,000 on filter paper.

Diverse ions: Iron(II) was detected without any interference from large excess of following ions: F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻, CNS⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SO₃²⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, tartrate, thiourea, NH₄⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Al³⁺, In³⁺, Tl⁺, Pb²⁺ and Mn²⁺.

Spectrophotometric determination of iron: To a suitable aliquot of iron solution, add 0.5 ml of 1% hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 3.0 ml of 0.02M ANP_mD solution and 2.0 ml of acetate buffer to adjust pH around 6.0 when it is finally made up to a desired volume. Measure its absorbance at 610 nm against a reagent blank prepared in the same way and calculate iron content from a calibrated curve.

Interferences: In determination of 1.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of iron, the following ions did not interfere to the extents ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) given in parentheses: CH₃COO⁻ or ClO₄⁻ (2,000); Cl⁻, Br⁻ or I⁻ (1,000); NO₂⁻ (800); Ca²⁺, Si²⁺, Ba²⁺, Al³⁺ or In³⁺ (500); NO₃⁻ (400); Mg²⁺ or Mn²⁺ (200); CNS⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, C₂O₄²⁻, tartrate, thiourea or Pb²⁺ (100); F⁻ (80); IO₃⁻ (50); Hg²⁺ (20); Cr³⁺ or Mo⁶⁺ (10) and BO₃³⁻, citrate or V⁴⁺ (5). The presence of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ or Pt⁴⁺ (50); Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Ru³⁺, Os⁸⁺ or Ir³⁺ (20); Au³⁺ (15) and Sn²⁺ or Rh³⁺ (10) could also be tolerated if 800 times molar excess of the ligand was used. In case of Ru³⁺ and Rh³⁺, it was necessary to measure the absorbance immediately after preparing the solutions. Ag⁺, after masking with Cl⁻, did not interfere up to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

The method was applied for determination of iron in alloys. The results obtained (Table 1) were within $\pm 0.5\%$ error.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRON IN ALLOYS

Alloy	Iron present (%)	Iron found (%)	Standard deviation
Nilo 'K' wire	53.14	53.10	0.005
Brightway G wire	22.50	22.62	0.008
BCS 214/1 Mn-Mo steel	97.23	97.32	0.002
BCS 224 Cr-V steel	96.65	96.76	0.005
BCS 232 Carbon steel	98.59	98.69	0.008
BCS 235/18/8 stainless steel	68.47	68.80	0.015
BCS 241/1	70.91	71.16	0.012

The blue colour of the complex was discharged by EDTA. This observation was applied in chelometric determination of iron using ANP_mD as indicator. The study shows that iron(II) solution with

concentration ranging between 40 μg and 10 mg of the metal, at pH 5.3–6.8, can be satisfactorily titrated against EDTA using about 0.5 ml of 0.01M ANP_mD indicator solution. The titration can be performed between 20°–25°. The disappearance of the blue colour indicated the end-point. In reverse titrations, which can also be performed, the end-point was given by the appearance of blue colour.

Chelatometric determination of iron : To iron solution (metal concentration 40 μg –10 mg) add 2.0 ml of 1% hydroxylamine hydrochloride (to reduce any Fe³⁺ present to Fe²⁺), adjust pH between 5.3 and 6.8 by adding 10.0 ml of acetate buffer and add 0.5 ml of 0.1M ANP_mD indicator solution. Dilute the solution to about 25 ml. Titrate slowly while shaking with standard EDTA when the blue colour completely disappears.

Interferences : In determination of 2.7920 mg of iron(II), which corresponded to 5.00 ml of 0.01M EDTA solution, the presence of 500 mg each of Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, CNS⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SO₃²⁻, tartrate, thiourea, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Al³⁺, In³⁺, Tl⁺, Sc³⁺ or Hg²⁺ (masked with I⁻); 300 mg of F⁻, S₂O₃²⁻ or Sn²⁺; 250 mg of Mn²⁺; 200 mg of BO₃³⁻; 70 mg of Cu²⁺ (masked with thiourea) and 20–25 mg of C₂O₄²⁻, Zn²⁺ (masked with tartrate) or V⁴⁺ (masked with F⁻) did not interfere. However, CN⁻, IO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, citrate, Cd²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mo⁶⁺ and platinum-group metals should be absent.

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Reference

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Studies on the Peptization of Oil-seeds of Saurashtra

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SEVERAL workers have extracted the nitrogenous constituents from oil free seeds, by means of various agents such as alkalis, acids and salt solutions. The process of extracting nitrogenous constituents from proteinaceous material is termed as peptization. This can throw light on the Indian method of cooking. During the cooking habits by how such nitrogen is peptized by addition of salt and other spices can be studied.

Smith *et al.*¹ extracted the nitrogenous matter from oil free soyabean meal by different acids and alkalis over a wide range of pH values. They also studied the protein for Alaska peas for peptization by various peptizing agents, at different pH. Fontaine *et al.*² studied the peptizability of the nitrogenous constituents of pea-nut meal.

Painter *et al.*³ studied the nitrogenous constituents of flaxseed and observed that salt solution dispersed between 43 to 81% of the nitrogen of finally ground oil free flaxseed meal.

Vasavada *et al.*⁴ studied the pulses of Gujarat for their peptization at different pH values. With different peptizing agents, Saxena *et al.*⁵ studied the vegetables and fruits of Saurashtra. They concluded that minimum dispersion of nitrogen is at 5.8 pH for proteins of Pomegranate and maximum dispersion of nitrogen at 12.2 pH of Tandalja with NaOH as a peptizing agent.

With the same background, few common oil-seeds of Saurashtra were taken for the study of peptization.

Some of the samples which have been selected are:—(1) Rapeseed; (2) Methiseed; (3) Groundnutseed; (4) Ajmaseed; (5) Sunflowerseed; (6) Tilseed (White variety); (7) Tilseed (Black variety); and (8) Tilseed (Red variety).

The results which have been recorded in the table have good correlation with the results of peptization worked out by other workers.

TABLE

Sr. No.	Oil-seeds	Minimum		Maximum	
		%	pH	%	pH
1.	Rapeseed	14.4	5.8	75.0	12.2
2.	Methiseed	19.0	5.8	85.5	12.2
3.	Groundnutseed	14.5	5.8	86.8	12.2
4.	Ajmaseed	9.5	5.8	89.1	12.2
5.	Sunflowerseed	5.7	5.8	81.0	12.2
6.	Tilseed (White Variety)	15.5	4.8	87.0	12.2
7.	Tilseed (Black Variety)	15.8	4.8	81.5	11.5
8.	Tilseed (Red Variety)	15.0	4.8	86.8	12.2

Experimental

Dry flour (4.0 g) were taken in an Erlenmeyer flask (250.0 ml) capacity. The peptizing agents were prepared from stock solution of acid, alkali and salt. The peptizing agent were added to the ground samples and the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.5, 4.8, 5.8 and 7.0 for hydrochloric acid (0.06N) as the peptizing agent and at pH 7.0, 8.5, 9.5, 10.5, 11.5 and 12.2 for the sodium hydroxide (0.1N) as peptizing agent. The pH of mixture was adjusted at 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 4.0, 5.8, 7.0, 8.5, 9.5, 10.5 and 11.5, respectively for the sodium chloride (1.0N).